

Ethical and Practical Trade-offs in Human Action Recognition Models for Assistive Systems

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Abstract—Human Action Recognition plays a vital role in assistive technologies deployed in real-world scenarios, where models must address challenges related to privacy, contextual reasoning, and robustness beyond controlled benchmarks. In this work, we introduce a novel taxonomy that classifies HAR models along two primary axes: the level of privacy ensured by the input modality and the model’s readiness for deployment in unconstrained environments. This classification is further informed by two semantic dimensions – temporal modeling and contextual awareness, which capture the model’s ability to reason over time and integrate environmental cues. Based on this taxonomy, we define the Privacy-Conscious Readiness and Modality Semantics score, a composite metric prioritising privacy while rewarding semantic richness and deployment feasibility. Our contribution enables a structured and ethics-aware evaluation of HAR models, facilitating their responsible use in assistive applications.

Index Terms—human action recognition, privacy preservation, deployment readiness, assistive systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Action Recognition (HAR) is increasingly central in assistive technologies, powering applications such as ambient assisted living, elderly care, smart environments, and driver monitoring. However, despite notable progress on standardised benchmarks, many HAR models are still disconnected from the realities of deployment in real-world scenarios – especially in privacy-sensitive contexts, where ethical considerations limit data collection and model transparency.

A critical gap exists between laboratory success and field applicability. Many state-of-the-art models rely heavily on raw visual inputs and are rarely tested outside curated datasets, where environmental complexity, user variability, and noise are minimised. Furthermore, current evaluation protocols tend to prioritise accuracy, often overlooking factors essential for deployment in assistive contexts, such as data privacy, resource efficiency, temporal reasoning, and contextual understanding.

To address these limitations, we introduce a novel taxonomy that evaluates HAR models not only in terms of technical performance but also in terms of deployment-critical dimensions. The taxonomy is organised along two primary axes

– **Privacy Level** and **Deployment Readiness** – and further informed by two complementary dimensions: **Temporal Modeling** and **Contextual Awareness**. Collectively, these criteria offer a more comprehensive assessment of model suitability for ethical and practical deployment in assistive technologies. In addition, we introduce the **Privacy-Conscious Readiness and Modality Semantics (PRMS)** score – a composite metric that quantifies a model’s potential for real-world, privacy-sensitive deployment. Through this taxonomy and scoring framework, we aim to guide the design and evaluation of HAR models where performance must be balanced with privacy, interpretability, and deployment feasibility.

The proposed taxonomy and scoring framework provide a classification for HAR models that is independent of their raw predictive accuracy on curated datasets. This approach uses a distinct set of criteria compared to traditional performance metrics, prioritizing a model’s suitability for real-world, privacy-sensitive assistive applications and acknowledging that high accuracy by itself does not guarantee ethical or practical applicability in these important domains.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a detailed overview of the selected HAR models, based on their input modalities. Section 3 describes the proposed taxonomy along with the Privacy-Conscious Readiness and Modality Semantics (PRMS) score. Section 4 provides the classification of selected HAR models with regards to the proposed taxonomy and addresses the implications and trade-offs between performance and ethical considerations for deployment ready applications. Section 5 provides conclusions and future work.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Ethical Evaluation Landscape for ML Models

This section acknowledges existing conceptual frameworks for ethical evaluation, while highlighting the limitations for offering quantifiable metrics.

For example, **AIES** [1] approach emphasizes the trade-off between **information gain**, **ethical harm**, and **cost**. The paper uses a utility function to represent this balance, but its main focus is on the conceptual challenges rather than providing a practical, quantifiable metric for models. It highlights that the components of the formula, such as ethical harm, are often difficult or impossible to quantify or agree upon. Furthermore,

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this framework is not specific to a particular domain, such as assistive systems.

Similarly, **am-ELO** [2] framework introduces a new ranking system to address the instability of the traditional ELO method, which is sensitive to data processing order. It uses **Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE)** approach to provide a more stable ELO score for model performance. The framework also incorporates **annotator abilities** to account for variability in human judgment, allowing it to estimate both model scores and annotator reliability. While this improves the fairness and reliability of the evaluation process by identifying anomalous annotators, it does not directly quantify ethical harms like privacy loss or bias in the model’s output.

B. HAR Solutions Overview

This section provides an overview for existing HAR solutions, categorized by their input modalities. The input data for training is a primary concern regarding privacy and real-world integration. However, it is essential to further examine the techniques models use to process this data to understand the impact of input modality on ethical aspects relevant to assistive applications.

Pose-centric Input

PO-GUISE [3] is a privacy-preserving action recognition model designed for use in semi-structured environments such as automotive or assistive contexts. It uses *pose estimation* to enhance both temporal reasoning and spatial attention. The model is based on a ViT-base architecture, initialized with pre-trained weights from VideoMAEv2 [4]. Optimization was performed using the AdamW optimizer with a Cosine Annealing learning rate scheduler. Loss functions included CrossEntropy for classification and log-scaled Mean Squared Error (MSE) for heatmap prediction (pose estimation). Nash-MTL [5] was employed to balance the two multi-task learning objectives: action recognition and pose estimation. Input video clips consisted of 16 frames, resized to 224x224 pixels. Human pose for each frame was estimated using ViTPose [6]. Evaluation was made on the following datasets: **Drive&Act** [7] (a multi-modal dataset with 34 fine-grained distracted driving activities during driving), **3MDAD** [8] (synchronized multi-modal and multi-view data, including “safe driving” and 15 distraction activities) and **HMDB-51** [9] (a general HAR dataset consisting of 6766 internet videos, with 51 action classes). Evaluated on the Drive&Act dataset, the model surpassed Transdarc [10] by 7.94% accuracy while reducing computational cost by 12 GFLOPS. On 3MDAD, it outperformed MIFI [11] by 5.35% accuracy with a 13 GFLOPS reduction. On HMDB-51, it performed comparably to BIKE [12] but with significantly reduced GFLOPS (269 GFLOPS vs. 932 GFLOPS).

Visual Input

Learnable Cube-Based Video Encryption [13] applies cube-based encryption strategies for privacy-aware video understanding. The method divides input video into *local spatio-temporal patches* and encodes them using *transformer-compatible encrypted tokens*. The architecture is based on two mechanisms: Learnable Cube-based Video Encryption

(LCVE) and ViT Scrambling. On one hand, privacy protection is offered by LCVE, through video encryption based on spatio-temporal cubes. Then, the ViT Scrambling process secures the Vision Transformer (ViT) [14] model itself, allowing it to process encrypted videos as effectively as unencrypted ones, without requiring any changes to the model’s architecture. To evaluate the ability to recognize actions in encrypted videos without performance degradation, evaluation was conducted on the following datasets: **Kinetics-400** [15], **UCF101** [16], **HMDB-51** [9], **Something-Something V2 (SSV2)** [17] and **Diving48** [18] (these are widely recognized benchmarks for action recognition). For privacy label prediction tasks, evaluation was performed on the following datasets: **IPN Hand** [19] and **KTH** [20]. For these datasets, the goal was to achieve lower prediction accuracy for hidden sensitive attributes.

Video-LLaVA [21] is a model that integrates video understanding with language generation capabilities. It processes *sequences of RGB frames* and generates *language-based explanations or responses* via vision-language alignment. The model is adaptable to open-ended tasks, such as describing ongoing events or answering questions about video input. The architecture uses encoders to pre-bind visual signals into the language feature space. The language encoders extract features from raw visual signals (images or videos) and initialize a module from OpenCLIP [22] to align images and language, relying on 3 million video-text pairs. The model learns from a mixed dataset of images and videos, mutually enhancing each other. Evaluation was conducted on widely recognized video question-answering datasets: **MSVD-QA** [23], **ActivityNet-QA** [24], **MSRVTT-QA** [25] and **TGIF-QA** [26]. The primary scenario involves open-ended tasks, such as describing ongoing events or answering questions about video input. The performance for these video question-answering tasks was assessed using ChatGPT-Assistant, following the methodology established by Video-ChatGPT (Maaz et al., 2023) [27]. The specific version of ChatGPT used was “gpt-3.5-turbo”. The model’s accuracy is qualitative, indicating descriptive evaluation. Video-LLaVA demonstrates better performance than Video-ChatGPT on MSVD (by 9.9%), MSRVTT (by 5.8%) and TGIF (by 18.6%) and demonstrates advanced performance compared to larger LLM models.

VideoMAE V2 [4] is a transformer-based masked auto-encoder designed for self-supervised video representation learning. It reconstructs *spatio-temporal patches of RGB video frames* using a ViT [14]-style transformer decoder. The architecture uses masked autoencoder designed for self-supervised video representation learning. The model uses a dual masking strategy for efficient pre-training, where the main components are an encoder operating on a subset of video tokens and a decoder processing another subset of video tokens. The reconstruction loss is computed only on the invisible tokens dropped by the encoder. The model performs video masked pre-training on a large unlabeled dataset and then post-pre-training on a labeled hybrid dataset. The model scales its backbone network from ViT-H to ViT-g

[28] (billion-level parameters). Evaluation was made on the following datasets: **Kinetics-400**, **Kinetics-600** [15], **UCF101** [16], **HMDB-51** [9], **Something-Something V2 (SSV2)** [17], **AVA** [29]. The primary scenarios include action classification, spatial action detection, and temporal action detection. VideoMAE V2 was evaluated using *top-1 accuracy* across these mainstream benchmarks and achieved state-of-the-art (SOTA) performances. For Something-Something V2, it significantly outperformed previous best performance, with over 7% improvement on Something-Something V1, achieving 77.0% accuracy. On AVA, it demonstrated better performance than previous masked modeling methods by 3.1%. On Kinetics, it achieved the best performance of 90% accuracy among compared methods without using extra in-house labeled data. On UCF101, it achieved the best performance of 99.6% accuracy and on HMDB-51 it obtained 88.1% accuracy.

Multi-modal Input

InternVideo2 [30] is a multi-modal model trained on *video, audio, and text*. It leverages contrastive and generative learning to align cross-modal embeddings at scale, being effective in pre-training for general-purpose video tasks and benchmark evaluations. The architecture uses a learning scheme involving three stages: video token reconstruction, multi-modal learning (including audio and text encoders), and next-token prediction. It is built upon a typical MLLM [27] architecture with a vision encoder, a vision-language connector, and a language model. For the ability to classify trimmed video clips into predefined action categories, evaluation was performed on the following datasets: **Kinetics-400**, **Kinetics-600**, **Kinetics-700** [15], **HMDB-51** [9], **UCF-101** [16] and **Something-Something V2 (SSv2)** [17]. For the ability to understand the semantic alignment between video content and natural language, evaluation was conducted on the following datasets: **ActivityNet** [31], **MSVD** [32], **LSMDC** [33], **DiDeMo** [34], **VATEX** [35]. For the ability to identify and precisely locate actions within untrimmed videos by predicting their start and end times, evaluation was made on the following datasets: **THUMOS14** [36] and **FineAction** [37]. The model’s performance was evaluated using *top-1 accuracy*, *Recall@1* for semantic alignment between video content and natural language and *mean Average Precision (mAP)* for video retrieval tasks. It achieves better performance than CLIP [38] methods on video semantics for both text-to-video (T2V) and video-to-text (V2T) on ActivityNet, MSVD, LSMDC, DiDeMo and VATEX.

III. MODEL TAXONOMY BASED ON PRIVACY AND DEPLOYMENT READINESS

To evaluate the applicability of HAR models in real-world assistive systems, we propose a taxonomy structured along two primary axes:

- ▶ **Privacy Level** — whether the model relies on sensitive data or privacy-preserving inputs.
- ▶ **Deployment Readiness** — whether the model has been evaluated in realistic or real-world settings beyond curated benchmark datasets.

In addition to these two axes, we define supporting dimensions that offer deeper insight into each model’s practical characteristics:

- **Temporal Modeling** — the degree to which a model captures sequential dependencies (e.g., short-term clip classification vs. long-term action reasoning).
- **Contextual Awareness** — whether and how the model leverages environmental, object-based, or semantic cues.

A. Protocols

We define rigorous protocols to ensure that the classification based on the proposed taxonomy is applied consistently and accurately across different models, minimizing subjective interpretation. Therefore, each composite will be characterized and quantitatively defined by specific numeric values.

Privacy Level: The privacy level for each model is determined based on the nature of its input data and the explicit anonymization techniques employed. Any steps taken before the data is used by a model, specifically designed to remove or obscure personally identifiable information (PII) or sensitive attributes, directly impact the input type that the model ultimately receives. Thus, we define the following privacy levels (summarised in Table I):

- **Low:** Assigned to models processing raw, identifiable visual or auditory data (e.g., raw RGB video, audio-text) without explicit anonymization. This input format carries a high risk of re-identification.
- **Medium:** Assigned to models utilizing input modalities that inherently offer some level of abstraction (e.g., pose data presented alongside visual elements) or apply basic, partial anonymization techniques. These reduce direct identifiability, residual information might still pose a risk.
- **High:** Assigned to models operating exclusively on highly abstract data representations (e.g., pure 3D skeleton graphs, ambient sensor data without visual/audio components) or implementing robust, explicit anonymization strategies (e.g., advanced encryption, region-based blurring/masking) that prevent re-identification while preserving action semantics.

TABLE I
INPUT MODALITY AND ASSOCIATED PRIVACY LEVELS

Privacy Level	Input Modality Examples
Low	raw RGB video audio-text
Medium	raw RGB video + pose
High	pose (e.g., joints coordinates of 3D skeletons) ambient sensor data (e.g., motion) region-based blurred/masked videos encrypted features

Deployment Readiness: The deployment readiness reflects whether the model has been evaluated under real-world conditions beyond laboratory or heavily curated settings:

- **No Testing:** Either the model has been evaluated exclusively on highly curated benchmark datasets collected

under controlled, scripted, or idealized laboratory conditions (e.g., UCF101 , NTU RGB+D , Kinetics datasets) – these datasets typically lack the noise, variability, and unpredictability of real-world environments, or the model has high computational demands for training (e.g., requiring high-end GPUs – more than 1 week).

- **Partial Testing:** The model has been evaluated on semi-naturalistic pre-recorded datasets that capture real-life activities (e.g., ActivityNet, MSVD datasets).
- **Fully Testing:** The model has been successfully deployed and validated for real-time inference in unconstrained assistive settings. This includes continuous operation in smart homes, in-cabin monitoring for drivers (e.g., Drive&Act dataset) , or demonstrated efficiency on wearable edge devices.

Temporal Modeling: The temporal modeling type reflects the model’s capacity to capture dependencies over time, defined as follows:

- **None:** Features are extracted from single frames, and either aggregated or used, discarding any temporal information inherent in the video sequence.
- **Short-Term:** The model can capture sequential dependencies over moderate durations (e.g., typical action classification clips, 1-3 seconds), distinguishing distinct, complete actions.
- **Long-Term:** The model is capable of reasoning over extended tasks or long-duration video sequences, understanding procedural or continuous actions and identifying relationships between sub-actions.

Contextual Awareness: The contextual level assesses the extent to which the model incorporates environmental, spatial, or task-related context, as follows:

- **None:** Focuses solely on human motion or isolated actions, disregarding surrounding objects or spatial layout.
- **Partial:** Leverages some scene elements, basic object interactions, but may not integrate semantic environmental understanding or nuanced task-specific contexts (e.g., knowing an object is present but not its specific affordance for the action).
- **Full:** Actively incorporates rich environmental, object-based, and semantic cues to understand actions within a broader context (e.g., using object states, room layout, or task instructions to infer complex activities). This is often demonstrated through the model’s ability to effectively answer complex questions about video content in QA datasets.

B. Classification

Using the primary dimensions, we categorized each model into one of four major classes based on its practical trade-off between privacy preservation and real-world applicability:

Class A — High Privacy, Fully Testing:

Models in this category rely on highly abstract data or robust anonymization and are successfully deployed or validated in real-world settings.

Class B — High Privacy, No/Partial Testing:

Models in this category operate on abstracted representations or implement anonymization strategies, but their evaluation was limited to simulated environments.

Class C — Low/Medium Privacy, Partial/Fully Testing:

Models in this category operate on identifiable visual or auditory data, but are validated in naturalistic scenarios.

Class D — Low Privacy, No Testing:

Models in this category rely on raw data and were evaluated on highly curated benchmark datasets only. They are primarily research prototypes or pretraining baselines with no proven field validation.

This taxonomy allows us to evaluate models not just by performance but by their alignment with ethical, contextual, and deployment-focused requirements relevant to assistive and human-centered applications.

C. PRMS: A Composite Score for Privacy-Conscious Action Models

To evaluate the deployment potential of HAR models in privacy-sensitive, context-rich environments, we introduce the **PRMS score**. This metric integrates the dimensions that reflect the requirements of ethical, real-world assistive applications: privacy level, deployment readiness, temporal modeling and contextual awareness.

Therefore, PRMS is computed as a weighted combination of the following components:

- **Privacy Level (P)** — Scored as 1 (Low), 2 (Medium) or 3 (High).
- **Deployment Readiness (D)** — Scored as 0 (No Testing), 1 (Partial), or 2 (Fully Testing).
- **Semantics (S)** — A composite of two subdimensions: temporal modeling and contextual awareness. It reflects the model’s ability to reason over time and leverage environmental or object-based cues.
 - **Temporal Modeling (T)** — Scored as 0 (None), 1 (Short-Term), or 2 (Long-Term).
 - **Contextual Awareness (C)** — Scored as 0 (None), 1 (Partial), or 2 (Full).

Semantics is computed as the average of these two components, as per the equation (1).

$$S = \frac{T + C}{2} \quad (1)$$

Scoring P from 1 to 3 is a deliberate choice to avoid the implications of an absolute “zero” value. Suggesting a total absence of privacy could be a strong and potentially inaccurate statement, given that most systems, even those using raw visual data, might have certain implicit safeguards (e.g., local storage, limited access). Therefore, we make a semantic and qualitative distinction, even though the mathematical normalization in the PRMS calculation makes the numerical contribution equivalent with with a scale starting from 0. This approach frames the lowest privacy tier as “Low Privacy” (represented by 1) rather than “Non-existent Privacy” (which

absolute zero imply).

Mathematical Reasoning for PRMS Weights

The Privacy-Conscious Readiness and Modality Semantics (PRMS) score is defined by the equation (2).

$$\text{PRMS}(i) = w_P \cdot P_{norm,i} + w_D \cdot D_{norm,i} + w_T \cdot T_{norm,i} + w_C \cdot C_{norm,i} \quad (2)$$

where i is an index representing a specific model being evaluated.

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Here, $P_{norm,i}$, $D_{norm,i}$, $T_{norm,i}$, $C_{norm,i}$ are normalized scores for each dimension (Privacy Level, Deployment Readiness, Temporal Modeling, Contextual Awareness) ranging from 0 to 1. The chosen weights are $w_P = 0.7$, $w_D = 0.2$, $w_T = 0.04999$, and $w_C = 0.04999$. This specific selection of weights (summing to approximately 1) is mathematically driven to achieve **strict class isolation** and enforce a **clear hierarchical structure** within the PRMS score’s classification. **Privacy Level** ($w_P = 0.7$): This is the dominant weight, ensuring that achieving a PRMS score sufficient for "High Privacy" classes (Class A: [0.9, 1] and Class B: [0.7, 0.9]) requires the maximum privacy level score. Without a significant privacy contribution, the maximum score from all other dimensions (Deployment Readiness, Temporal Modeling, Contextual Awareness) is insufficient to reach these top tiers.

Deployment Readiness ($w_D = 0.2$): This weight is designed to maintain a greater influence on the score, even for partially tested models, than the combined weights of Temporal Modeling and Contextual Awareness ($w_T + w_C \approx 0.1$). This mathematically prevents advanced semantic understanding alone from compensating for a lack of real-world deployability. Models with high semantic scores but low deployment readiness will be limited to low tiers, ensuring practical readiness to be prioritized for higher classifications.

Temporal Modeling ($w_T = 0.04999$) and **Contextual Awareness** ($w_C = 0.04999$): These dimensions, while contributing to nuanced understanding, are given smaller, equal weights. Their combined influence is deliberately chosen to prevent class over-classification, reinforcing the PRMS score’s focus on ethical and practical readiness as primary considerations.

Using the primary dimensions, we categorize each model into four classes – Class A (High Privacy, Fully Testing), Class B (High Privacy, No/Partial Testing), Class C (Low/Medium Privacy, Partial/Fully Testing), and Class D (Low Privacy, No Testing) – reflecting the trade-offs between privacy preservation and real-world applicability. As illustrated by Figure 1, these classes are defined by the following PRMS score intervals: **Class A**: [0.9, 1], **Class B**: [0.7, 0.9), **Class C**: [0.1, 0.65), **Class D**: [0, 0.1)

Fig. 1. PRMS Score Classification Intervals

The weighting scheme for the PRMS score is meticulously designed to reflect the strategic priorities for HAR models

intended for ethical, real-world assistive systems. Each factor is normalized to a [0,1] range. The final PRMS score is calculated as per the equation (3).

$$\text{PRMS}(i) = 0.70 \cdot \frac{P_i - 1}{2} + 0.20 \cdot \frac{D_i}{2} + 0.09999 \cdot \frac{S_i}{4} \quad (3)$$

IV. EVALUATION

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of the selected HAR models within the framework of our proposed taxonomy and PRMS score.

A. Classification of Models Using the Proposed Taxonomy

We will now apply previously defined protocols to classify each selected model into one of the four categories (A, B, C, or D), ensuring a consistent and systematic evaluation.

– Class A: High Privacy, Deployment Ready –

PO-GUISE [3] belongs to Class A due to both its focus on pose estimation as a privacy-preserving input and its successful integration within semi-structured, realistic settings. By prioritizing *pose-centric inputs* and minimizing reliance on raw RGB data, it maintains a strong privacy profile across multiple tasks. The model has been validated on the *Drive&Act* dataset, which simulates real-world human-vehicle interactions, and has shown effective performance in those settings. Its proven applicability in realistic deployment scenarios qualifies it as both **high-privacy** and **fully-tested for unconstrained assistive settings**.

– Class B: High Privacy, No/Partial Testing –

Learnable Cube-Based Video Encryption (WACV 2024) [13] belongs to Class B due to its lacking evaluation in practical settings, despite its rigorous implementation of privacy-preserving mechanisms over input data. The model provides a **high-privacy** protection level by *preventing visual re-identification*, even when applied to RGB videos. However, the model has only been tested on academic datasets such as *HMDB51* and *UCF101*. As a result, it demonstrates strong potential for privacy-aware video modeling but remains **not yet tested in real-world settings**.

– Class C: Low/Medium Privacy, Partial/Fully Testing –

Video-LLaVA [21] belongs to Class C due to its sensitive input modality, despite its evaluation within partially realistic scenarios. The model relies on *unfiltered visual data* and does not include privacy-preserving mechanisms such as anonymization or masking. It has been tested on datasets covering a variety of naturalistic settings (daily activities, events, and scenes that reflect *real-world visual data*), supporting its deployment readiness. Video-LLaVA is thus positioned as **partial tested in real-world settings** but has **low-privacy** level.

– Class D: Low Privacy, Not Deployment Ready –

VideoMAE V2 [4] belongs to Class D since it operates directly on *unfiltered RGB video* and lacks any built-in privacy mechanisms, while being evaluated only in laboratory settings. The model achieves high accuracy on standard benchmarks such as *Kinetics-400*, but it has not been evaluated in realistic scenarios. As such, VideoMAE V2 has **low-privacy** level with **no testing in real-world settings**, being a benchmark-oriented model.

InternVideo2 [30] belongs to Class D as it lacks any privacy preserving mechanisms, being trained on vast amounts of *uncurated web data*, while evaluated only for general-purpose video tasks. The *costly computational requirements* for training and inference make it unreliable for real-world applications, despite the fact that the model was validated for semantic alignment on datasets reflecting real-world. InternVideo2 remains a large-scale research model with **low-privacy** alignment and **no testing in real-world scenarios**.

B. Breakdown of Dimensional Composites for PRMS Score

To emphasize the criteria outlined in our taxonomy, we will calculate the PRMS score for each model. For clarity and transparency, we will detail how each composite dimension is assigned its specific numerical value for every model.

InternVideo2: Privacy Level (P = 1): Lacks explicit privacy mechanisms and is trained on vast amounts of uncurated web data. **Deployment Readiness (D = 0):** The model has been tested on video question-answering datasets which simulate real-world scenarios. However, the model imposes high computational training demands, requiring significant GPU resources (e.g., 256 NVIDIA A100 GPUs and 18 days for Stage 1, 14 days for Stage 2; 64 A100 GPUs for 3 days in Stage 3). **Temporal Modeling (T = 2):** Strong for long-form video understanding and explicitly evaluated on Temporal Action Localization datasets like THUMOS14 and FineAction, where it gets the highest mAP among all comparisons. **Contextual Awareness (C = 2):** Excels in video-related dialogue and is evaluated on multi-choice video QA benchmarks.

VideoMAE V2: Privacy Level (P = 1): Processes unfiltered RGB video. Its primary objective is learning generic video representations for various downstream tasks, with no explicit built-in privacy mechanism. **Deployment Readiness (D = 0):** Focuses on research benchmarks with no explicit testing in real-world scenarios. **Temporal Modeling (T = 2):** Leverages a ViT backbone with joint space-time attention. **Contextual Awareness (C = 0):** The model does not integrate semantic information beyond pixel-level reconstruction for explicit contextual understanding.

Video-LLaVA: Privacy Level (P = 1): Processes raw RGB video frames and image inputs. Its design does not explicitly implement privacy-preserving mechanisms. **Deployment Readiness (D = 1):** The model has been tested on video question-answering datasets which simulate real-world scenarios. The training required 8 A100-80G GPUs for 3-4 days, pushing it to a partially deployment readiness state. **Temporal Modeling (T = 1):** Processes video inputs by

uniformly sampling 8 frames from each video. **Contextual Awareness (C = 2):** It is explicitly evaluated on multi-choice video QA benchmarks and outperforms Video-ChatGPT on these datasets, demonstrating a strong ability to understand semantic aspects.

Learnable-Cube: Privacy Level (P = 3): Explicitly designed for high privacy by performing shuffling operations on spatio-temporal cubes and shuffling pixel values. This allows it to achieve low prediction accuracy for private attributes (e.g., 4.0% for actor labels on KTH Dataset), effectively hiding visual information. **Deployment Readiness (D = 0):** Evaluated on academic datasets only, and lacks explicit validation in real-world deployment scenarios. **Temporal Modeling (T = 1):** Operates on spatio-temporal cubes of dimension $2 \times 16 \times 16$ pixels, incorporating temporal information. Its primary focus is on cryptographic-like scrambling rather than advanced temporal reasoning for complex long-form video understanding. **Contextual Awareness (C = 0):** The core objective is scrambling spatio-temporal features for the purpose of making content incomprehensible to attackers. It does not focus on broader contextual understanding, object interaction reasoning, or multi-modal dialogue capabilities.

PO-GUISE: Privacy Level (P = 3): Explicitly designed for high privacy by analyzing driver behavior through human pose information rather than raw RGB data. It leverages human keypoint location heatmaps to select the most informative video tokens, reducing unnecessary visual exposure. **Deployment Readiness (D = 2):** Validated on real-world driving datasets like Drive&Act and 3MDAD. **Temporal Modeling (T = 1):** Processes video clips consisting of 16 frames using joint space-time cube embedding. This allows for establishing a holistic temporal context, though its primary focus is on driver action snippets rather than long video understanding. **Contextual Awareness (C = 1):** The use of semantic information from human keypoint locations supports action recognition involving object interaction, but without a rich environmental understanding.

Based on Table II, the proposed protocols facilitate the computation of the PRMS score, allowing its mapping into predefined class categories.

TABLE II
PRMS SCORE AND CLASS CATEGORY FOR SELECTED HAR MODELS

Model	P	D	T	C	PRMS Score	Class
VideoMAE V2	1	0	2	0	≈ 0.05	D
InternVideo2	1	0	2	2	≈ 0.10	D
Video-LLaVA	1	1	1	2	≈ 0.175	C
Learnable-Cube	3	0	1	0	≈ 0.725	B
PO-GUISE	3	2	1	1	≈ 0.95	A

C. Model Scale and PRMS Score: A Trade-Off with Deployment Readiness

The model scale, quantified by the number of parameters, directly affects the PRMS score in an inverse relationship. Models with a high number of parameters lead to higher computational demands for both training and inference (training

can take weeks or months, and inference requires substantial processing power). This generates increased latency during inference, thus the **Deployment Readiness (D)** dimension, a key component of the PRMS score, should be affected negatively.

We collected the number of parameters for the selected models, as presented in Table III. From this data, we concluded that models with a higher number of parameters (e.g., in the billions) consistently present lower PRMS scores, whereas models with a smaller parameter count (e.g., in the tens or hundreds of millions) generally achieve higher PRMS scores. This observation strongly validates the inverse relationship between model scale and the PRMS score, showing the significant impact of large parameter counts on computational demands and latency, which directly reduce a model’s deployment readiness.

TABLE III
PARAMETERS COUNT AND PRMS SCORE FOR SELECTED HAR MODELS

Model	#Params	PRMS Score
VideoMAE V2	1.011B	0.05
InternVideo2	6B	0.10
Video-LLaVA	7B	0.175
Learnable-Cube	85-87M	0.725
PO-GUISE	86M	0.95

#Params: Total count of all weights and biases.

D. Accuracy and PRMS Score: A Trade-off with Privacy Level

While achieving high accuracy is a primary objective in Human Action Recognition (HAR), a singular focus on maximizing performance on benchmark datasets can introduce a critical trade-off with the PRMS score, particularly concerning the **Privacy Level (P)** dimension.

Models aiming for the highest possible accuracy on standard benchmarks often do so by processing raw and identifiable visual or auditory data. On the other hand, privacy-preserving techniques, such as anonymization (e.g., region-based blurring, masking) or operating on highly abstract data representations (e.g., 3D skeletons, encrypted features), while crucial for privacy, can make the input more challenging for the model. This complexity might lead to a perceived reduction in accuracy compared to models that operate on raw data.

This highlights that models achieving peak performance by not implementing robust anonymization or by using raw identifiable data may result in a low PRMS score, as their focus on accuracy compromises the ethical and practical requirements prioritized by the proposed taxonomy.

The Table IV serves as a central reference for comparing the empirical performance of HAR models across diverse datasets and validation techniques.

Considerations for Bias in Accuracy Estimation: Accurate evaluation of machine learning models demands careful consideration of potential biases in performance estimation, as highlighted in [39]. They concluded that standard **K-fold**

TABLE IV
MODEL EVALUATION SUMMARY

Model	Dataset	Dataset Size	#Cls	Val Technique	Accuracy
VideoMAE V2	Kinetics-400	241,181 / 38,671 (Val: 19,877)	400	Standard Splits	90.0% Top-1
	HMDB51	3,570 / 1,530 (Val: 1,666)	51	Standard Splits	88.1% Top-1
	UCF101	9,536 / 3,783	101	Standard Splits	99.6% Top-1
	SSV2	168,913 / 27,157 (Val: 24,777)	174	Standard Splits	77.0% Top-1
InternVideo2	Kinetics-400	241,181 / 38,671 (Val: 19,877)	400	Standard Splits	92.1% Top-1
	HMDB51	3,570 / 1,530 (Val: 1,666)	51	Standard Splits	80.7% Top-1
	UCF101	9,536 / 3,783	101	Standard Splits	97.3% Top-1
	SSV2	168,913 / 27,157 (Val: 24,777)	174	Standard Splits	77.5% Top-1
	ActivityNet	15,000 / 5,000	200	Standard Splits	74.1% (T2V R@1) 69.7% (V2T R@1)
	MSVD	1,200 / 670 (Val: 100)	1,970	Standard Splits	61.4% (T2V R@1) 85.2% (V2T R@1)
Video-LLaVA	ActivityNet-QA	N/A	N/A	Zero-shot Evaluation	45.3% Acc.
	MSVD-QA	N/A	N/A	Zero-shot Evaluation	70.7% Acc.
Learnable-Cube	Kinetics-400	241,181 / 38,671 (Val: 19,877)	400	Standard Splits	80.3% Top-1
	HMDB51	3,570 / 1,530 (Val: 1,666)	51	Standard Splits	70.0% Top-1
	UCF101	9,536 / 3,783	101	Standard Splits	95.6% Top-1
	SSV2	168,913 / 27,157 (Val: 24,777)	174	Standard Splits	69.0% Top-1
	Diving48	15,026 / 1,970	48	Standard Splits	86.2% Top-1
PO-GUISE	HMDB51	6,766 videos, 3-fold splits	51	Cross-Validation	82.83% Acc.†
	Drive&Act	12 hours, 3-fold splits	34	Cross-Validation	63.24% Macro Acc.†

#Cls: Number of classes in the given dataset.

Val Technique: Validation method used to assess model performance.

†Accuracies obtained using K-fold Cross-Validation may be optimistically biased, especially with smaller dataset sizes, as discussed in the article of reference [39].

Cross-Validation often implies *strongly biased and overoptimistic* accuracy estimates. In contrast, **standard splits** methods produce *unbiased* results, regardless of sample size.

This optimistic bias in K-fold Cross-Validation primarily stems from overfitting when model development steps (e.g., feature selection, hyperparameter tuning) are performed on data pooled across training and validation folds. The problem is most severe with smaller sample sizes, but persists for larger ones. Consequently, PO-GUISE’s accuracies, derived using K-fold Cross-Validation, require cautious interpretation regarding potential optimistic bias.

The study [39] established this via systematic simulations, generating Gaussian noise data – with 50% theoretical accuracy, and varying the sample sizes. By comparing K-fold Cross-Validation against unbiased methods (Train/Test Split, Nested CV), they empirically demonstrated that K-fold Cross-Validation consistently generates accuracies significantly above 50%, indicating optimistic bias. For example, K-fold Cross-Validation showed a bias ($B_{K-fold}(N) = Acc_{observed} - Acc_{true}$) of ≈ 40 percentage points at $N = 20$, decreasing to ≈ 15 percentage points at $N = 1000$, while the standard splits showed almost null optimistic bias.

Our purpose in incorporating this analysis is to acknowledge the potential impact of optimistic bias inherent in K-fold Cross-Validation, which directly affects the reported accuracies of PO-GUISE. We performed a comparative simulation between the observed optimistic bias, derived from collected values across various sample sizes, and a mathematical power function. This power function models the relationship with sample size and serves as a theoretical fit to the empirical optimistic bias data, as shown in the Figure 2. The objective in fitting this power function is to mathematically approximate the impact of the optimistic bias across varying sample sizes, providing a continuous model for understanding how this bias affects the accuracy as the sample size increases.

Based on the Figure 3, we can observe the relationship between a model’s PRMS score and its accuracy across common datasets. Among the compared models, lower PRMS

Estimated Optimistic Bias ($B_{K-fold}(N)$) vs. Sample Size (N)

Fig. 2. Estimated Optimistic Bias in Accuracy for K-fold CV as a function of Sample Size. Data based on the study [39].

scores tend to correlate with higher accuracies. Each cluster of colored bars along the X-axis represents a specific model, identified by its PRMS score and name, while the individual bars within each cluster indicate the accuracy achieved by that model on a particular dataset (as per the legend). This visualization highlights that, in general, models with lower PRMS scores (indicating lower privacy and deployment readiness) tend to correlate with higher raw benchmark accuracies on traditional datasets. PO-GUISE’s accuracy on HMDB51, evaluated using 3-fold Cross-Validation, is subject to optimistic bias as discussed by [39], and further illustrated in the figure.

Models in Class A and Class B (higher PRMS, prioritizing privacy) tend to have lower raw benchmark accuracies compared to models in Class C or Class D (lower PRMS).

Accuracies for ActivityNet and MSVD are more complex to compare across models, due to their varied task types. Despite this, their PRMS score still reflects their fundamental design choices in terms of input data type and any privacy-preserving mechanisms.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The analysis conducted in this paper demonstrates that privacy-preserving and deployment-ready HAR models form a distinct category that cannot be fully captured by traditional performance metrics alone. The proposed taxonomy clarifies how factors such as input modality, temporal modeling, and contextual awareness influence the practical applicability of HAR systems in sensitive assistive environments.

The proposed PRMS score effectively highlights the gap between benchmark performance and real-world readiness, emphasising the need to consider privacy and deployment constraints as first-class criteria in model evaluation. Models prioritising abstracted inputs align better with ethical requirements and deployment feasibility.

PRMS Score vs. Accuracy by Dataset for Common Models

Fig. 3. Accuracies of models on common datasets, grouped by their PRMS Score. Bars for each dataset originate from the model’s PRMS score on the X-axis.

Overall, this work underscores the importance of shifting focus from purely accuracy-driven assessments toward more holistic evaluation frameworks that integrate privacy, semantics, and operational readiness. This approach offers a significant advancement over existing methods, which represents high-level conceptual frameworks that discuss trade-offs without providing quantifiable metrics, or evaluation systems that focus on model stability and performance without directly addressing the whole spectrum of sources for ethical concerns. Our work distinguishes itself by providing a structured, quantifiable metric that directly integrates privacy, semantics, and operational readiness into a single, comprehensive score. Such an approach is essential to enable the responsible and effective use of HAR technologies in assistive applications.

Future work will focus on improving the fairness and reliability of performance evaluation in HAR by correcting biases introduced through cross-validation, especially in scenarios involving datasets of varying sizes. We intend to develop and apply correction methods that yield more representative performance estimates, enabling consistent and equitable comparisons across models.

We also plan to investigate the trade-offs between semantic richness and privacy. This includes studying how models can retain strong temporal and contextual reasoning capabilities while operating on privacy-preserving inputs, such as anonymised or abstracted data. Furthermore, we will assess how different anonymisation techniques affect model accuracy and explore architectural strategies that mitigate the privacy-accuracy trade-off.

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